

Computational Solutions for Systematic Literature Review Conduction Support in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping

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Table 1: List of included studies

ID	Title	Year	Reference
1	Emerging Results on Automated Support for Searching and Selecting Evidence for Systematic Literature Review Updates	2024	[24]
2	A Semi-automatic Screening Mechanism for Literature Review	2023	[3]
3	Assessing expert system-assisted literature reviews with a case study	2022	[38]
4	Developing research questions in conversation with the literature: operationalization e tool support	2022	[7]
5	SCAS-AI: A Strategy to Semi-Automate the Initial Selection Task in Systematic Literature Reviews	2022	[27]
6	Tell Me How to Survey: Literature Review Made Simple with Automatic Reading Path Generation	2022	[8]
7	slr-kit: A semi-supervised machine learning framework for systematic literature reviews	2022	[12]
8	Incorporating Altmetrics to Support Selection and Assessment of Publications During Literature Analyses	2022	[33]
9	SeSG: a search string generator for Secondary Studies with hybrid search strategies using text mining	2022	[2]
10	A framework for the application of machine learning in IS literature reviews	2022	[5]
11	The application of Machine Learning in literature reviews: a framework	2022	[6]
12	STaR Approach for Supporting Analysis and Synthesis in Collaborative Literature Reviews	2022	[9]
13	Supporting systematic literature reviews using deep-learning-based language models	2022	[1]
14	A comprehensive framework to reinforce evidence synthesis features in cloud-based systematic review tools	2021	[29]
15	CrowdSLR: A tool to support the use of crowdsourcing in systematic literature reviews	2021	[31]
16	ASH: A New Tool for Automated and Full-Text Search in Systematic Literature Reviews	2021	[34]
17	Automatically Generating Citation Graphs (and Variants) for Systematic Reviews	2021	[18]
18	Reducing efforts of software engineering systematic literature reviews updates using text classification	2020	[37]
19	Information retrieval methodology for aiding scientific database search	2020	[21]
20	An SLR-tool: search process in practice: a tool to conduct and manage systematic literature review (SLR)	2020	[19]

ID	Title	Year	Reference
21	Toro: A Web-based Tool to Search, Explore, Screen, Compare and Visualize Literature	2020	[23]
22	Thoth: A Web-based Tool to Support Systematic Reviews	2019	[20]
23	Evaluating strategies for forward snowballing application to support secondary studies updates - Emergent results	2018	[15]
24	Using Suffix Tree Clustering Method To Support The Planning Phase Of Systematic Literature Review	2017	[16]
25	Beyond the spreadsheet: Reflections on tool support for literature studies	2016	[35]
26	Improvements in the StArt tool to better support the systematic review process	2016	[10]
27	Semi-automatic selection of primary studies in systematic literature reviews: is it reasonable?	2015	[28]
28	DASyR(IR) - Document analysis system for systematic reviews (in Information Retrieval)	2015	[30]
29	A method to support search string building in systematic literature reviews through visual text mining	2015	[22]
30	SESRA - A web-based automated tool to support the systematic literature review process	2015	[26]
31	Supporting systematic reviews using LDA-based document representations	2015	[25]
32	Using rule-based classifiers in systematic reviews: a semantic class association rules approach	2015	[32]
33	Visual Text Mining: Ensuring the Presence of Relevant Studies in Systematic Literature Reviews	2015	[14]
34	Slrtool: A tool to support collaborative systematic literature reviews	2014	[4]
35	Automatically locating results to support systematic reviews in software engineering	2013	[36]
36	Managing Literature Reviews Information through Visualization	2012	[11]
37	Using visual text mining to support the study selection activity in systematic literature reviews	2011	[13]
38	SLR-Tool a tool for performing systematic literature reviews	2010	[17]

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